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Development of Communicative Skills in Mentally Retarded Children of Preschool Age as a Pedagogical-Psychological Problem

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***Abstract:** In this article, the pedagogical and psychological problems of developing communicative skills in mentally retarded children of preschool age are covered through the scientific theoretical analysis of the cognitive processes of children with mental retardation and the research of correctional methods of education and upbringing of this category of children.*

***Keywords:** perception, memory, attention, imagination, speech, psychological and pedagogical support, communicative skills.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of communicative skills in preschool children with intellectual disabilities as a pedagogical and psychological problem requires special approaches and methods. These children deviate from their normal path of development and face difficulties in communicating and expressing their thoughts. To effectively implement this process, it is necessary to harmonize pedagogical and psychological approaches.

The psychological characteristics of mentally retarded students in national special psychology and pedagogy have been studied by G.B. Shoumarov, K.K. Mamedov, L.R. Muminova, M.F. Khakimova, D.A. Nurkeldiyeva, and other scholars [3, 4, 7]. Students with intellectual disabilities are characterized by insufficient development of cognitive interests, which manifests itself in their less need for knowledge than their normal peers. At all stages of the cognitive process, students with intellectual disabilities exhibit underdeveloped mental functions, and in some cases, elements of atypical development. As a result, students with intellectual disabilities have an incomplete, sometimes distorted, understanding of the surrounding world.

Abu Ali ibn Sina was the first to put forward the idea that mental functions depend on the activity of certain centers in the brain and tried to scientifically prove it. He believed that animals and humans, unlike the plant world, possess the ability to perceive external forces. This ability is manifested

through three different forces: the force that moves the body, the driving force, the general force (related to visual, auditory, sensory, gustatory and olfactory activity) and the force of reason (which includes imagination, memory, and reason). Each of these forces is associated with a certain part of the brain, and the disease of a part of the brain is associated with it, causing a failure of force activity [2].

According to Abu Nasr al-Farabi, the theory of cognition, that is, human cognition, is governed by the brain's mental ability, and the heart is the center that provides all organs with the blood necessary for life. A person acquires all knowledge from outside. It has many tools and possibilities for this: intuition, memory, imagination, logical thinking, reason and speech - with the help of these tools, a person masters sciences [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Complex forms of dementia arise from a combination of underdeveloped brains and brain damage. In such cases, intellectual disability is accompanied by a number of neurodynamic and encephalopathic disorders. In addition, impaired cerebral hemispheric function may include underdeveloped or damaged speech, cognition, praxis, spatial perceptions, computational skills, reading, and writing [5].

The perception of intellectually disabled students is not sufficiently active, poorly differentiated, only external signs of objects are perceived, and the formation of categories of color, form, size, and quantity takes a long time. Time and space orientation are disrupted, and it is evident that visual perception is formed in a narrow circle. They are observed in the following diseases: illusions, hallucinations, disorders of gnostic perception (visual, medial, tactile, auditory agnosia). Psychologists A.D. Vinogradova, N.L. Kolomensky, and others note that mentally retarded people, unlike their peers with normal intelligence, are characterized by limited perceptions of the surrounding world and primitive interests.

Perception is inextricably linked to thought and is the fundamental foundation of cognition. It arises in the form of actions such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, abstraction, and concretization. Not all of these operations are sufficiently developed for children with intellectual disabilities. Thus, they analyze objects randomly, omitting a number of important features, highlighting only the most significant parts. With such random analysis, they find it difficult to identify connections between parts of the topic [6].

A distinctive feature of students with intellectual disabilities is the inability to think critically and evaluate their work independently. They often don't notice their mistakes and usually don't realize their failures.

The memory of mentally retarded children differs somewhat from the memory of healthy children. Several scientists who have studied the memory characteristics of intellectually disabled children have noted that memory characteristics can be developed depending on the level of intellectually disabled children. The use of small hand tools for developing memory in preschool children with intellectual disabilities yields effective results [2].

Types and processes of memory also acquire specific content based on the time, degree, and nature of brain damage in a mentally retarded child. Therefore, the memory characteristics of each child are unique. One of the main conditions for eliminating memory deficiencies in mentally retarded children is to make the knowledge given to them interesting [1].

The specific attention span of mentally retarded children depends on many factors. The characteristics of higher nervous function, the core signs of mental retardation (minimal mobility of nervous processes, weakness of the dominant, impaired aiming), leave a deep mark on the course of his entire

personal development, leading to the analysis of attention. Attention deficiencies leave their complications in speech. Such children do not pay attention to their own and their peers' speech [2].

Attention shows the manifestation of this connection, as well as the focus of consciousness on the source. According to L.S. Vgotsky, a violation of higher forms of attention in mentally retarded children is a violation of the connection between biological and cultural development. To successfully carry out corrective work with children with intellectual disabilities, knowledge of the physiological mechanisms of a child's attention is required. In mentally retarded children, voluntary attention is inferior to involuntary attention. This is due to the weakness of internal braking and the pronounced appearance of external braking. External braking, which is difficult to control, leads to attention deficit in children with intellectual disabilities [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students with intellectual disabilities, knowing that they speak differently from others, try to use speech less. This negatively affects the development of communication skills. Children with intellectual disabilities have difficulty communicating with adults and other children. They don't fully understand what others are saying, and consequently, they don't behave as if they need to. Their communication occurs in limited, everyday, repetitive situations.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that students with intellectual disabilities suffer not only from the communicative sphere, but also from other spheres of life due to the disruption of all higher mental functions. Deviant behavior, problems of social adaptation, impaired self-esteem - all of this can be observed in a student with low communication skills without timely prevention, correction, and psychological and pedagogical assistance.

Based on an analysis of the aforementioned literature on the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the problem of developing communicative skills in mentally retarded preschool children, we present the following pedagogical and psychological aspects of the problem and their solutions:

Pedagogical problems:

1. **The need for an individual approach:** Each child has their own needs and abilities. Therefore, they require an individual approach, the development of special curricula and methods.
2. **Special Educational Programs:** Lack of special educational programs aimed at developing communicative skills for children with intellectual disabilities or the need to improve existing programs.
3. **Lack of resources:** The lack of specialized pedagogical materials, tools and equipment is often a problem. These children need adapted books, games, and audiovisual materials.
4. **Teachers' qualifications:** Teachers lack sufficient knowledge and skills to work with children with special needs. It is necessary to organize professional development courses and trainings.

Psychological problems:

6. **Lack of self-confidence:** Children with intellectual disabilities often underestimate themselves by comparing them to other children and may be afraid to communicate. This creates a need for self-confidence and psychological support.
7. **Low motivation:** In order to develop communicative skills, it is important to motivate children and arouse their interest. This requires special methods and incentive systems.

8. **The Role of Family and Society:** The role of parents and society in communicating with children with intellectual disabilities is important. Family members should also receive special trainings and advice.
9. **Psychological support:** It is necessary to develop and implement special programs to provide psychological assistance to children, to help them cope with stress and anxiety.

CONCLUSION

Developing communicative skills in children with intellectual disabilities as a pedagogical and psychological problem requires special approaches and resources. To successfully implement this process, educators, psychologists, and parents must work together.

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